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Assessment of Maritime Safety and Security in the Transportation of Seaborne Oil Trade in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of maritime safety and security on the transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria. Given Nigeria's heavy dependence on oil exports and imports transported via tanker vessels, the study investigates how safety incidents (tanker accidents) and security challenges (piracy and vandalism) affect the performance of the oil and gas (O&G) maritime sector. A quantitative research design was adopted using 15 years (2006–2020) time-series secondary data sourced from the Nigerian Ports Authority, Department of Petroleum Resources, International Maritime Bureau, and International Tanker Owners' Federation. Analytical techniques included incidence rate modeling and multiple regression analysis. The Findings of the study reveal significant levels of maritime incidents, with an average annual tanker accident rate of 41.7, pirate attacks at 10.0, and vandalism incidents at 2307.87. Results indicate that vandalism constitutes the most dominant security threat. Regression analysis shows that maritime safety and security incidents significantly influence the demand for tanker vessels ($R^2 = 0.62$), seaborne oil export ($R^2 = 0.55$), import trade ($R^2 = 0.71$), and crude oil prices ($R^2 = 0.66$). While accidents and vandalism negatively affect tanker demand and trade volumes, piracy showed mixed effects. Furthermore, safety and security challenges significantly influence global crude oil prices. The study concludes that persistent maritime insecurity and safety lapses undermine the efficiency and sustainability of Nigeria's seaborne oil trade. It highlights the need for stronger regulatory enforcement, improved maritime surveillance, and investment in safety infrastructure. The findings contribute empirical evidence to policy discourse on maritime risk management in Nigeria's O&G sector

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Maritime Safety, Maritime Security, seaborne oil Trade, Tanker Vessels, Offshore Operations.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is an oil and gas producing State and prominent member of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). The Nation's economy is believed to be driven majorly by proceeds from investment in the oil and gas industry. The Nation is also reputed to have the largest investment in the offshore upstream oil and gas industry in the West and Central African regions. However, just as the Country is a prominent exporter of crude oil and gas resources, it is also a major importer of refined petroleum products in the West and Central African region; given her huge economy and population. Both the export of crude oil and gas resources from the export terminals and the importation of refined petroleum products to Nigeria through the maritime terminals and seaports; occur by shipping it over the oceans by the use of tanker vessels of varied sizes. The demand for oil tankers (tanker vessels) for the purposes of transporting both refined and crude oil over the seas to and from Nigeria is viewed as derived from shippers (oil marketers) demand to ship crude and refined oil resources (seaborne oil trade). The concept of seaborne oil trade in the context of this study therefore encompasses the exchange (export and import) of crude oil and refined petroleum products between Nigeria and her trading partners, the transportation which is general done through crude and product tanker shipping over the seas. This trade is facilitated through the oil and gas export terminals and the seaport terminals (Ndikom, Nwokedi, Nnaji, Gbasibo, Olusegun, 2018). Ndikom, *et al.*, (2018) and Guerrierco, (2012) note, that while the export of crude oil in Nigeria are handled at the oil export terminals, the import of refined petroleum product is also handled by many dedicated marine jetties, both being managed by the Nigerian ports Authority (NPA) in various locations, offshore in Nigeria.

Notwithstanding the very importance of seaborne oil export and import trade in the economic life of Nigeria as a Nation, the Oil and Gas (O&G) industry in Nigeria has over the years been confronted with several safety and security challenges that have impacted negatively on the wheels of development of the sector and the Nigerian economy in general. The upstream crude production operations in Nigeria for example is known to have been negatively impacted by insecurity in the Nigeria maritime domain, ranging from deliberate vandalism attacks on offshore O&G installations to pirate attacks against tanker vessels involved in the transportation of seaborne oil trade to demand markets in Nigeria and overseas. There are also issues of safety associated with upstream productions as well as transportation operations of the operators, as poor work procedures have oftentimes led to accidents with serious consequences of oil spill and environmental pollution. Regulators have oftentimes failed to show adequate capacity to address these maritime safety and security challenges confronting the optimal performance of the O&G sector in Nigeria.

Maritime safety in this context is viewed as the processes, policies, procedures, regulations and practices implemented in the upstream maritime environment, on oil production and transportation facilities and infrastructure such as tanker vessels, Floating production and offloading system (FPSO) etc., in order to protect the infrastructure from accidental failures and incidences. Thus, all processes, policies, procedures and regulations implemented onboard tanker vessels involved in transportation of seaborne oil trade as well as those implemented to ensure the safe operation of the O&G production and transportation systems fall under maritime safety operations. The central goal of implementing maritime safety onboard vessels is to eliminate or limit the occurrence of accidents. The occurrence maritime accidents/incidents therefore provide evidence of the lack of safety in the operations of any ship operator, whether in the transportation of seaborne oil trade or other types of shipping trade. Accidents have implications and impacts on the operations of the shippers and producers of both crude oil and refined petroleum products. Therefore, the performances of the maritime safety regulators cum ship operators in limiting the occurrence of tanker accidents through the diligent implementation of maritime safety regulations and policies have direct implications on the directions and operations of seaborne oil export and import trade in Nigeria. It is important to empirically examine the aforementioned relationship.

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Similar to maritime safety, maritime security entails the protection of the maritime domain and investment in the maritime sector to deliberate criminal exploitation, attacks, and damages. In the O&G sector, deliberate vandalism of oil production and transportation installations, pirate attacks on tanker vessels transporting oil, criminal breaking of oil pipeline infrastructure, illegal unregulated bunkering, militancy and acts of terrorism, etc., represent acts of insecurity and criminal exploitation with negative implications on the development of the sector in Nigeria. Maritime security and safety as a broad policy arena can equally involve a broad range of activities, including fisheries and resource governance, environmental protection, mitigating the effects of climate change, as well as combating terrorism and piracy (Engel, 2014). Maritime insecurity can be linked to premeditated activities that are counterproductive and inimical to the ocean economy. In recent years however, maritime insecurity in Nigeria waters has metamorphosed into organized attacks against the Oil and Gas industry leading the vandalism of oil and gas infrastructure. Thus, vandalism attacks aimed at the offshore oil and gas infrastructure and attacks on oil tankers transporting seaborne oil trade in the Nigeria maritime domain constitute key metrics for assessing influences of maritime security in the development of seaborne oil and gas trade in Nigeria (Nwokedi et al, 2020).

Though maritime safety and maritime security each have different approaches and regulations in combating it in the maritime industry, they impose the same consequences in the shipping industry; which is the fact that both marine accidents as proxies for level of safety in shipping operations and pirate attacks on tankers cum vandalism of offshore oil and gas infrastructure leads to damages of investment and waste of resources. This study is therefore cast to assess influences of maritime safety and security in the transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria.

Over the years, the upstream oil and gas industry in Nigeria including the lifting of crude oil from the export terminals to overseas demand markets have faced the challenges of insecurity in the Nigeria maritime domain. The challenges of militancy and terrorism in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria culminated into piracy and armed robbery attacks against ships involved in oil production and transportation in Nigeria, leading serious negative economic consequences for the nation and underdevelopment of the O&G sector. The situation is similar in the transportation of refined petroleum products to Nigeria over the seas. Statistics by the International Maritime Bureau (IMB, 2019) reveal increasing trend in attack of petroleum product tankers in the Nigeria maritime domain of the Gulf of Guinea region. Attacks and vandalism of offshore O&G production and transportation infrastructure have serious economic consequences and implications on the trend of operations in the shipping export and import trade of crude and refined oil. Similarly, statistical reports from the International Federal of Marine Tanker owners suggests increasing trend in frequency of accidents and oil spill involving marine tanker vessels the Nigerian maritime domain. This indicates the prevalence of safety challenges in the industry, indicating further that, existing maritime safety regulations and practices have not been adequately implemented to limit the occurrence of marine tanker accidents and the consequent oil spill and environmental damages. These have implications on the optimal performance of the seaborne oil trade sector in Nigeria since oil transportation activities show significant influence in the directions of growth and performance of the petroleum industry in Nigeria.

The aforementioned problems requires research and empirical information to be able to provide and develop the right knowledge and strategies to overcome the negative effects of maritime safety and security challenges on the transportation of seaborne oil export and import trade in Nigeria. However, most of the needed empirical knowledge to guide against the negative consequences of maritime safety and security challenges in seaborne transportation of oil and gas trade is lacking. For example, available empirical literatures have over the years failed to provide adequate information on the level of safety and security incident rates, affecting industrial vessels types and oil tanker involved the transportation of Nigeria seaborne oil trade as basis for understanding the extent to

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which maritime insecurity and tanker accidents have influenced operations in the sector. Also lacking in available empirical literature is the information of the significance of the influence of maritime safety and security challenges on the trend of demand for tanker vessels for the transportation of seaborne oil export and import trade in Nigeria. Issues bordering on oil tanker accidents, vandalism of oil and gas infrastructure, pirate attacks against ships in the Gulf of Guinea maritime domain and other maritime safety and security issues are understood to have implications on the charter rates for industrial vessels for servicing the needs of the offshore oil and gas industry as well as on crude oil prices in the global market; yet available empirical literatures seems to have failed to provide convincing information and knowledge of to what extent these maritime safety and security challenges relate with and influence vessel charter rates and crude oil prices. These are the central problems which the study has identified and which it seeks to provide solutions to.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to assess the effects of maritime safety and security in the transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria

The specific objectives of the study include:

- (i) To evaluate the safety and security incident rates of vessels involved in transportation of Nigerian seaborne oil trade.
- (ii) To assess the influences of maritime safety and security incidents on the demand for oil tanker vessels in the Nigerian O&G industry.
- (iii) To model the relationship Nigeria's seaborne oil trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents.
- (iv) To determine the influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigeria on the trend of crude oil prices.

1.2 Research Questions

- (i) What is the extent of maritime safety and security incident rates of vessels involved in transportation of Nigerian seaborne oil trade?
- (ii) To what extent do maritime safety and security incidents influence the demand for oil tanker vessels in the Nigerian O&G industry?
- (iii) What is the extent of the relationship between Nigeria's seaborne oil trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents?
- (iv) What is the level of influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigeria on the trend of crude oil prices?

1.4 Hypotheses

- (i) The extent of maritime safety and security incident rates of vessels involved in transportation of Nigerian seaborne oil trade is indeterminate
- (ii) There is no significant influence of maritime safety and security incidents on the demand for oil tanker vessels in the Nigerian O&G industry?

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- (iii) The relationship between Nigeria's seaborne oil trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents is not significant.
- (iv) The influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigeria on the trend of crude oil prices is not significant.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

There are scanty empirical literature reviews on maritime piracy. However, Nnadi, et al. (2015) analyzed maritime piracy and armed robbery in the Gulf of Guinea region from 2002 to 2015. They used a time-series data of 14 years on the reported piracy and armed robbery attacks in the 15 Gulf of Guinea countries and nine coastal zones of Nigeria. A Trend analysis model and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data. From their findings, it was observed that there was significant variation in piracy and armed robbery attacks among the Gulf of Guinea countries, of which the greatest number of attacks occurred in Nigeria. They also noted that there was also a significant variation in piracy attacks among the coastal zones of Nigeria with attacks in Lagos ports and anchorages being highest within the period under review.

Etus (2016) used the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Simple regression methodology to model the relationship between Nigeria's economic growth (RGDP) and piracy incidents in Nigerian waterways. Her findings depict that there is an inverse relationship between the two variables such that, RGDP will decrease by 16.8% for every one percent increase in piracy activities in Nigerian waterways, though the relationship between the variables is not statistically significant. Okeahalam & Otwombe (2016) used general estimating equations (GEE) modeling to access factors that determine the risk of piracy attacks. They accessed mainly the impact which the level of economic and institutional development in several regions may have on the frequency and success and failure rates of piracy attacks. They found that the frequency of piracy attacks is higher in regions where the quality of institutions is low and that most attacks take place close to a port. Furthermore, their findings depict that successful attacks are most likely in regions that are poor and have low military capacity.

Sascha et al. (2013) studied the contributing factors of maritime piracy by analyzing previous incidents that have been reported to the International Maritime Organization (IMO). Part of the analysis is to filter those ship types that are particularly vulnerable to piracy attacks. The paper also introduces the guidelines developed by the IMO and the industry envisaging minimizing the risk to ships that are exposed to attacks from pirates. It further describes the initiatives taken to develop a sustainable mechanism in the high-risk area (HRA) to suppress piracy and other maritime crimes.

Wong & Yip (2012) used data from ICC International Maritime Bureau (IMB) from 2002 to 2009 with the aid of binary choice models to estimate the success/failure of pirates' attacks as a function of vessel type, flag, vessel operation, number of pirates, boarding methods, and arms type. They used the binary models to quantify how pirates' characteristics and behavior determine the rate of success and degree of violence of pirates attacks. Their results identified three major approaches for pirates' attacks, with the different approaches being associated with different levels of violence, arms used and different targets. It further shows that bulk carriers, general cargo ships, containerships, chemical tankers, and tankers are favorite targets, and these types of vessels account for 76% of all ships attacked from 2002 to 2009.

Jon & Shannon (2014) compared successful and unsuccessful pirates attacks for 4,638 observations against ships worldwide and the situational factors that help prevent such attacks. Their findings show that when a ship's crew takes proactive self-protective measures that increase the perceived effort (increasing speed, employing evasive maneuvers) and increase the

perceived risk (embarking private security, having watchman present, raising alarm, increasing lighting, anti-piracy) of perpetrating an attack, unsuccessful attacks are significantly more likely after controlling for environmental influences.

Beloff (2013) noted that Somalis turn to piracy due to poor economic reasons. He further explained that the fall of the Somali government in 1994 marked the advent of piracy in Somali waters. Gries & Redlin (n/a) examined the effects of socio-economic, political, and institutional conditions on maritime piracy for 149 countries between 1991 and 2010 by applying random-effects negative binomial regression. Their results show that, on average, less developed countries with higher political and institutional disorder have a higher probability of piracy attacks. They identified that there exist negative effect of GDP on piracy, suggesting that weak economic development causes piracy, the positive relationship between trade openness and piracy indicates that as trade increases, piracy increases. They also found that dependence on fishery is negatively correlated with piracy, indicating that a decrease in fishery yields results to increase in piracy activities.

Al-Qattan (2016) investigated maritime piracy in the Arabian Gulf and Somalia with a practical objective of understanding the drivers underpinning piracy behavior to aid in identifying how best to deal with the issue. The main findings from empirical data collected using face-to-face semi-structured interviews for 43 observations (undertaken between 2012 & 2013 in Kuwait, Qatar, Bahrain, Dubai, Abu Dhabi, Nairobi, and Mombasa) showed that pirates could be categorized according to different strategies adopted in attacking ships: pirates in the Arabian Gulf applied hit and run techniques, while Somalis' pirates adopted a kidnap for ransom approach.

Shane, Piza & Silva (2017) used data from the international maritime bureau to examine which vessels are most at risk of a pirate attack and ransom demand, the relationship between attacks for ransom and violence, which countries experience the most attacks for ransom, the effects of situational crime prevention (SCP) techniques on injuries during attack and the effects of SCP on ransom demands. Their findings show that SCP is a useful strategy for reducing episodes of ransom and injuries, highlighting how SCP techniques can be adapted in unique environments when other traditional crime control resources are unavailable.

Essien and Adongoi (2015) examined Sea Piracy and Security Challenges of Maritime Business Operation in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Research hypotheses were tested using regression analysis. The result showed a significant negative effect of pirate attacks on sea business operations. Hence, adequate security should be provided for sea business operations to facilitate sea business operations in Nigeria. Rami (2010) examined piracy and its impact on the economy with the use of the political economy method. This thesis has shown that piracy has had a large impact not only physically, but financially on society as a whole.

Furthermore, Jiang (2014) examined maritime piracy in Malacca Strait and the South China Sea. He used series hazard modeling and multivariate logistic models to test the relative strengths of deterrence and reactance models for the risk of piracy attacks under a military intervention and several major events. He found significant evidence for the conclusion that the rate of piracy attacks reduced significantly when direct controls are implemented to reduce the environmental opportunities of crime, and when the certainty effect becomes stronger. He further noted that the only exception is when pirates are highly motivated. Also, the results support the reactance perspective when the odds of successful attacks significantly increase after the anti-piracy military intervention was introduced.

Udensi, Etu, and Chieke (2014) examined national security and maritime piracy in Nigeria: A sociological discourse. The discourse used secondary data from

International Maritime Bureau (IMB) to show the severity and pattern of piracy in Nigeria waterways, and the tenets of the three capability gap thesis found out that while corruption is the major cause of maritime piracy and insecurity in Nigeria, election malpractices specifically equips the pirates with arms directly or indirectly.

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3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative research design method in which time series secondary data was used for the study. Secondary data on the proxies for maritime safety and insecurity which include pirate attacks against tankers ships trading in Nigeria and vandalism-attacks on offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria, number accidents involving tankers vessels used in the transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria were collected and used. Similarly, time series secondary data on barrels of oil export trade from Nigeria, tonnage of oil import trade handled by the ports in Nigeria were collected from the Nigerian Port and Authority (NPA) as proxies for seaborne oil trade. Also time series data on the demand for oil tankers in Nigeria, crude oil prices and charter rates for industrial vessels servicing the transport need needs of O&G sector in Nigeria were collected. Each dataset covered a period of 15 years from 2006 and 2020. In each case, the proxies for maritime safety and security were used as the independent variables while the proxies seaborne oil trade cum crude oil prices, demand for tanker vessels and vessel charter rates were used as dependent variables.

The data used for this study were sourced through the Secondary sources. The various sources from which data was collected include the Nigeria Port Authority Annual statistical report from were data on tanker vessel traffic to Nigeria ports and tonnage of oil import trade handled were collected, the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) from were data of oil export trade through the export terminals and vandalism attacks against offshore oil infrastructure were collected, the International Maritime Bureau annual statistical reports from where data on pirate attacks against ships trading in Nigeria were collected, The International Federation of oil tanker owners (ITF) from where data on tanker accidents in Nigeria and charter rates of industrial vessels were collected.

3.3. Methods of Data Analysis

3.3.1: The Incidence Rate Model

The Incident rate Model provides direct measure of the occurrence of maritime accident affecting vessels involved in transportation over time, even with the implementation of the maritime safety measures, procedures and policies over the same period. Incidence refers to occurrence of new cases of industrial vessel accident or pirate attack upstream oil and gas infrastructure accident leading to damages to the trade and fleet of operators, in the course of implementation maritime safety regulations, policies and procedures over a given time frame. The population incidence rate is defined as the number of new cases of vessel accident and damages or pirate attacks or vandalism attacks occurring, that will affect vessels in the fleet, in a specified time interval, divided by the sum of observation times, in that interval, on vessels in the fleet of the operator, that were free from accident at the beginning of the time interval (NRC, 2006). In general, vessel accident or incidence rate is time dependent and depends on both the starting point and the length of the interval as well as the effect of maritime safety regulations, procedures and polices carried out on the vessels over the period (NRC, 2006).

Thus, if the period over which a vessel in the oil tanker fleet accident record in the course of implementing safety measures is T_n divided into T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 periods; and the number of tanker vessels in the fleet of the operator is N out of which X vessels suffered accident security attacks, even in the course of implementing safety rules, the incident rate (**IR**) is determined as:

$$IR = \frac{X}{\sum T_1 + T_2 + \dots T_n}$$

$$= \frac{X}{\sum T_n} \tag{1}$$

The denominator T_n is an approximation to the sum of observation time periods over the observed number of vessels in the fleet that had accident or affected by pirate attacks and in practice is usually replaced by the actual observation time, which accounts for the fact that the incident did not occur exactly at the same time (NRC, 2006). Using the IRM, the rate of oil tanker accidents, the rate of maritime security incident and the rate of vandalism incidents affecting vessels servicing the transportation needs of the O&G sector will be determined in line with the first objective of the study.

3.3.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

The OLS multiple regression method was used to investigate the relationship between maritime safety and security incidents in seaborne oil transportation in Nigeria, and the demand for tanker vessels for transportation of seaborne oil trade. The model specification is as follows:

$$VESEL_{dmd} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACCDT_{rate} + \beta_2 PIRATE_{attacks} + \beta_3 VANDALISM_{attacks} + e \quad (2)$$

Where:

$VESEL_{dmd}$ = demand for oil tanker vessels in Nigeria O&G sector

$ACCDT_{rate}$ = tanker vessel accidents in Nigeria Maritime domain

$PIRATE_{attacks}$ = pirate attacks on oil tanker vessels

$VANDALISM_{attacks}$ = vandalism attack on offshore oil and gas infrastructure

β_0 = regression constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = coefficients of regression

e = error term

Since some of the variables in the dataset are not in the same units; they were transformed into Natural log (Ln) equivalents in order to implement the multiple regression analysis. The regression analysis defines the relationship between the dependent and independent variables for each of the research objectives for the years under study and was used to obtain the coefficients associated with the Nigerian maritime sector.

The model specifications are as follows:

$$\ln OILEXPTRADE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln ACCDT_{rate} + \beta_2 \ln PIRATE_{attacks} + \beta_3 \ln VANDALISM_{attacks} + e \quad (3)$$

The above model was used to investigate the relationship between seaborne oil export trade and maritime safety cum security incidents in Nigerian maritime domain. To determine the influence of maritime safety and security incidents on seaborne oil import trade we used the equation:

$$\ln OILIMPTRADE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln ACCDT_{rate} + \beta_2 \ln PIRATE_{attacks} + \beta_3 \ln VANDALISM_{attacks} + e \quad (4)$$

To estimate the effects of maritime safety and security incidents on crude oil prices was estimated using the equation below:

$$\ln CRUDEPRICES = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln ACCDT_{rate} + \beta_2 \ln PIRATE_{attacks} + \beta_3 \ln VANDALISM_{attacks} + e \quad (5)$$

The sign and value of the estimators indicate the proportionate direction and magnitude of effect each independent variable (input) will have on the dependent variable (output). For instance, a positive sign will indicate a direct proportionate effect.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table1: Safety and Security Incident rates of Operating Tanker Vessels in Nigeria Offshore Oil and Gas Sector

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Accidentrate	15	32.00	23.00	55.00	41.7333
pirateattack	15	6.0	7.0	13.0	10.067
Vandalism	15	2864.00	836.00	3700.00	2307.8667
attackothers	15	21.00	27.00	48.00	38.4667
oilprices	15	68.77	40.68	109.45	74.2487
vesselcharterrates	15	11000.00	5000.00	16000.00	10836.6667
tankertraffic	15	1427.00	2133.00	3560.00	2988.0667
oilexporttrade	15	251000000.00	631000000.00	882000000.00	781007060.4667
oilimporttrade	15	11496989.09	9633472.14	21130461.23	16246215.5780
Valid N (listwise)	15				

Descriptive Statistics

	Std. Deviation
Accidentrate	8.88391
pirateattack	1.7099
Vandalism	939.33585
attackothers	5.87813
oilprices	24.07027
vesselcharterrates	3415.43067
tankertraffic	384.41095
oilexporttrade	71328658.17983
oilimporttrade	3745832.78817
Valid N (listwise)	

Source: Author's calculation

The result of the study shown on table1 indicates that between 2006 and 2020 covered in the study, an average of 41.7 tanker vessels transporting seaborne oil export and import trade get involved in accidents in Nigeria per annum while the mean number of pirate attacks against vessels transporting seaborne oil trade is 10.0 get attacks annum with a standard deviation of 1.70. The mean vandalism attacks against offshore oil and gas infrastructure per annum over the period in 2307.87 attacks with standard deviation of 939.33.

Similarly, the average price of crude oil traded in the market over the period was \$74.2487 with a standard deviation of 24.07 while the mean charter rate for offshore O&G service vessels in the spot market over the period is \$10836.67 with standard deviation of 3415.43. The mean number of tankers vessels involved in the trading of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria ports and terminals between 2006 and 2020 is 2988.0667 tankers per annum with standard deviation of 384.41 while the average seaborne oil export trade carried by the tankers from the export terminals to overseas countries is 781007060.466 barrels per year. The average tonnage of seaborne oil import trade handled over the same period is 16246215.578 tons with standard deviation of 3745832.788.

By implications, the incident rate of oil tanker vessels trading in the Nigeria maritime domain with regards to the occurrence of accident (safety incident rate) is approximately 41.7; indicating that an average of 41.7 oil tanker vessels involved in the carriage of Nigerian oil export and import trade get involved in marine accidents in the shores of Nigeria. Similarly, the security incident rate of tanker vessels trading in Nigeria with regards to pirate attacks against oil tankers is an average of 10.0 attacks per annum. This implies that at least, 10.0 out of the tanker vessels involved in the carriage of Nigerian seaborne oil export and import trade get attacked by pirates each year. The incident rate of

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vandalism attacks against the general oil and gas infrastructure in the Nigeria maritime domain is an average of 2307.87 attacks per annum. These incidents are expressed in percentages as shown in table2 below.

Table2: Incident Rates of safety and Security Challenges in the Offshore O&G Sector in Nigeria

Accident/safety incident rate of oil tankers in Nigeria as % of total incidents in the O&G sector	Security incident rate in the O&G sector	
	Incident rate of pirate attacks on oil tankers as % of total O&G sector incidents	Incident rate of vandalism attacks as % overall O&G sector incidents
1.79%	0.43%	97.78%

Source: Author’s calculation

The result of the study the table2 indicates that the percentage safety incident rate which measures the percentage of tanker accidents per annum affecting the transportation seaborne oil export and import trade as percentage of total safety and security incidents in the O&G sector is about 1.79% while pirate attacks against tankers trading in the Nigeria waters has incidents rate of about 0.43%. Vandalism attacks against all the infrastructures in the offshore O&G sector in Nigeria, including pipeline infrastructures transporting oil to the export terminals has an incident rate of 97.78% when compared with oil tanker accidents and pirate attacks against oil tankers.

Table3: Comparing the Safety and Security Incidents in the Shipping of Seaborne Oil Export and Import Trade for Significant Differences

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	pirateattack	10.067	15	1.7099	.4415
	attackothers	38.4667	15	5.87813	1.51773
Pair 2	Accidentrate	41.7333	15	8.88391	2.29382
	pirateattack	10.067	15	1.7099	.4415
Pair 3	pirateattack	10.067	15	1.7099	.4415
	Vandalism	2307.8667	15	939.33585	242.53547
Pair 4	Accidentrate	41.7333	15	8.88391	2.29382
	Vandalism	2307.8667	15	939.33585	242.53547

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
		Lower			
Pair 1	pirateattack - attackothers	-28.40000	4.20544	1.08584	-30.72889
Pair 2	Accidentrate - pirateattack	31.66667	9.36305	2.41753	26.48158
Pair 3	pirateattack - Vandalism	-2297.80000	939.85722	242.67009	-2818.27558
Pair 4	Accidentrate - Vandalism	-2266.13333	939.30589	242.52774	-2786.30360

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
		Upper				
Pair 1	pirateattack - attackothers	-26.07111	-	26.155	14	.000
Pair 2	Accidentrate - pirateattack	36.85175	-	13.099	14	.000
Pair 3	pirateattack - Vandalism	-1777.32442	-	-9.469	14	.000
Pair 4	Accidentrate - Vandalism	-1745.96307	-	-9.344	14	.000

Source: Author's calculation

The table3 above compared the incident rates of accidents (safety incidents) and security incidents (Pirate attack against oil vessels and vandalism attacks against all O&G infrastructure) to determine if significant differences exist. It also compared pirate attacks against ship transporting other trade types and ships transportation oil export and import trade. The result shows that there is a mean difference of -28.4 attacks with a standard deviation of 4.20 between the number of ships transporting other trade types attacked by pirates and the number of tanker vessels transporting seaborne oil trade that was attacked by pirates over the 15 years period covered in the study. The implication of the negative coefficient of the difference (-28.4) is that ships trading in other commodity types other than oil, were attacked 28.4 times, more than ships trading in oil. The t-score of 26.071 and p-value of 0.00 indicates that there is significant difference between pirate attacks against ships trading in other commodity types than ships trading in seaborne oil trade. In a The result reveals that there is a significant difference between accident rate of oil tankers in the Nigeria maritime domain and pirate attacks against tanker vessels trading in the

seaborne oil export and import trade in Nigeria. The accident rate of oil tankers is 31.85 times higher than the rate of pirate attacks against oil tankers over the period covered in the study. Similarly, the rate of vandalism attacks against the overall offshore O&G industry infrastructure is 1777.32 times significant higher that the rate of pirate attacks against oil tanker vessels alone. The rate of vandalism attacks against the overall O&G industry infrastructure is equally significantly higher than the average rate of accidents involving oil tankers by 1745.963.

Table4: Influence of Maritime safety and Security Incidents on the Demand for Oil Tankers in the Nigeria Shipping Industry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.821 ^a	.672	.519	339.79139	2.097

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	798764.882	3	266254.961	4.306	.033 ^b
Residual	1270040.052	11	115458.187		
Total	2068804.933	14			

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	3422.072	879.057		3.893	.003	
Accidentrate	-.338	10.430	-.008	-.032	.975	-.025
pirateattack	14.444	56.881	.064	.254	.804	.248
Vandalism	-.245	.102	-.599	-2.410	.035	-.618

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2634.9521	3330.9707	2988.0667	238.86112	15
Residual	-513.33722	455.50299	.00000	301.19287	15
Std. Predicted Value	-1.478	1.436	.000	1.000	15
Std. Residual	-1.511	1.341	.000	.886	15

a. Dependent Variable: tankertraffic

The result shown in Table-4 above shows the influence of Maritime safety and Security incidents on the demand for oil tankers in the Nigeria oil export and import trade. The result shows that the coefficient of correlation R which measures the degree of correlation between maritime safety and security and demand for oil tanker vessels is 0.821. it indicates the existence of about 82% correlation between maritime safety cum security and demand for oil tanker vessels for shipping Nigeria’s seaborne oil export and import trade.

The model showing the relationship depicting the influence of maritime safety and security on demand for oil tanker vessels for shipping Nigeria’s seaborne oil export and import trade between 2006 and 2020 is:

$$VESEL_{dmd} = 3422.072 - 0.338ACCDT_{rate} + 14.44PIRATE_{attacks} - 245VANDALISM_{attacks} \quad (6)$$

This implies that a unit annual increase in maritime accidents in the Nigerian maritime domain leads to decreasing trend in demand for oil tanker for the shipping of Nigeria’s seaborne oil export and import trade by 0.338 units while with a 1 unit increase in pirate attacks against oil tankers trading in

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Nigeria maritime domain, demand for oil tankers for shipping Nigeria’s seaborne oil trade is still increase by 14.44 units. Similarly, a unit increase in vandalism attacks against the overall offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria leads to a 245 units decrease in the demand for oil tankers for the carriage of Nigeria’s seaborne oil export and import trade.

The implication is that increasing oil tanker accidents and vandalism attacks against oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria maritime domain decreases the demand for oil tanker in the Nigerian seaborne oil trade sector. However, increasing pirate attacks against vessels trading in seaborne oil and gas sector in Nigeria does not lead to decreasing trend in demand for oil tankers.

The coefficient of determination R^2 which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.621. This indicates that about 62% variation in the demand for oil tankers in the Nigeria offshore O&G industry is explained by maritime safety and security incidents and challenges in the sector. The relationship between seaborne oil export trade and maritime safety and security challenges in the Nigerian maritime domain is presented in table5 below.

Table5: Relationship between Seaborne Oil Export Trade and Maritime Safety cum Security Incidents in Nigerian Maritime Industry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.742 ^a	.551	.346	.19723	2.236

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	.023	3	.008	3.796	.042 ^b
1 Residual	.104	11	.009		
Total	.127	14			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21.547	.794		27.131	.000
	LOGACCIDENTRATE	-.130	.115	-.318	-1.134	.281
	LOGPIRATEATTACKTANKE RS	-.196	.155	-.362	-1.266	.232
	LOGVANDALISM	-.018	.057	-.091	-.326	.750

a. Dependent Variable: LOGOILEXPORTRADE

Source: Author’s calculation

The result showed in Table5 above shows the relationship between Seaborne oil export trade and maritime safety cum security incidents in Nigerian maritime Industry. The result shows that the coefficient of correlation R which measures the degree of correlation between maritime safety and security and quantum of seaborne oil export trade handled by the terminals is 0.742. It indicates the existence of about 74% correlation between maritime safety cum security and barrels of seaborne oil export trade handled by the oil export terminals in Nigeria over the period.

The model showing the relationship depicting the influence of maritime safety and security on quantum of seaborne oil export trade handled by the terminals between 2006 and 2020 is:

$$InOILEXPTRADE = 21.55 - 0.130InACCDT_{rate} - 0.196InPIRATE_{attacks} - 0.018InVANDALISM_{attacks} \tag{7}$$

This implies that a 1% annual increase in maritime accidents in the Nigerian maritime domain leads to decreasing trend in the quantum (in barrels) of seaborne oil export trade handled in the oil export

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terminals in Nigeria by 0.130% while with a 1% increase in pirate attacks against oil tankers trading in Nigeria maritime domain, quantity of seaborne oil export trade handled in the oil export terminals decreases by 0.196%. Similarly, a percentage increase in vandalism attacks against the overall offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria leads to a 0.018% decrease in the quantity of seaborne oil export trade handled at the terminals.

The implication is that increasing oil tanker accidents, increasing trend of vandalism attacks against oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria maritime domain and increasing rate of pirate attacks against oil tanker vessels trading in Nigeria, leads to decreasing trend in quantity (in barrels) of seaborne oil export trade handled in the oil export terminals.

The coefficient of determination R^2 which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.55. This indicates that about 55% variation in the quantity of seaborne oil export trade handled by the export terminals is explained by maritime safety and security incidents and challenges in the sector. The relationship between seaborne oil import trade and maritime safety and security challenges in the Nigerian maritime domain is presented in table6 below.

Table6: Relationship between Seaborne Oil Import Trade and Maritime Safety cum Security Incidents in Nigerian Maritime Industry

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.845 ^a	.714	.521	.65828	2.731

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.181	3	.060	4.905	.040 ^b
	Residual	.734	11	.067		
	Total	.915	14			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.625	2.110		9.303	.000
	LOGACCIDENTRATE	-.346	.305	-.314	-1.135	.280
	LOGPIRATEATTACKTANKERS	-.165	.412	-.113	-.401	.696
	LOGVANDALISM	-.181	.150	-.333	-1.207	.253

a. Dependent Variable: LOGOILIMPORTRADE

The result showed in Table6 above shows the relationship between Seaborne oil import trade and maritime safety cum security incidents in Nigerian maritime. The result shows that the coefficient of correlation R which measures the degree of correlation between maritime safety and security and quantum of seaborne oil export trade handled by the terminals is 0.845. It indicates the existence of about 85% positive correlation between maritime safety cum security and seaborne oil import trade handled by the oil port terminals in Nigeria over the period.

The model showing the relationship depicting the influence of maritime safety and security on seaborne oil import trade handled by the port terminals between 2006 and 2020 is:

$$InOILIMPTRADE = 19.63 - 0.346InACCDT_{rate} - 0.165InPIRATE_{attacks} - 0.181InVANDALISM_{attacks} \quad (8)$$

This implies that a 1 percent annual increase in maritime accidents in the Nigerian leads to decreasing trend in the seaborne oil import trade handled in the port terminals in Nigeria by 0.346% while with a 1percent increase in pirate attacks against oil tankers trading in Nigeria maritime domain, seaborne oil import trade handled in the port terminals decreases by 0.165%. Similarly, a 1 percent increase in vandalism attacks against the overall offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria leads to a 0.181% decrease in the seaborne oil import trade handled at the terminals.

The implication is that increasing oil tanker accident, increasing trend of vandalism attacks against oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria maritime domain and increasing rate of pirate attacks against oil tanker vessels trading in Nigeria, leads to decreasing trend seaborne oil import trade handled in the oil export terminals. This is not healthy for the development of the O&G sector as well as the port logistics and maritime sector in Nigeria.

The coefficient of determination R^2 which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.714. This indicates that about 71% variation in the seaborne oil import trade handled by the port terminals is explained by maritime safety and security incidents and challenges in the sector. The influence of maritime safety and security on trend of crude oil prices in the sector over the years is presented in table7 below.

Table7: The Influence of Maritime Safety and Security Incidents on Trend of Crude oil Prices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.814 ^a	.663	.571	.22007	2.051

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1.048	3	.349	7.216	.006 ^b
1 Residual	.533	11	.048		
Total	1.581	14			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.953	1.797		1.087	.300
	LOGACCIDENTRATE	.753	.260	.519	2.894	.015
	LOGPIRATEATTACKTANKER	-.813	.351	-.425	-2.316	.041
	LOGVANDALISM	.180	.128	.252	1.409	.187

a. Dependent Variable: LOGOILPRICES

The result showed in Table7 above shows the influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigerian waters on the trend of crude oil prices in the O&G sector. The result shows that the coefficient of correlation R which measures the degree of correlation between maritime safety and security and crude oil prices is 0.814. It indicates the existence of about 81% positive correlation between maritime safety cum security incidents and crude oil prices between 2006 and 2020.

The model showing the relationship depicting the influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigeria on crude prices in the global market between 2006 and 2020 is:

$$InCRUDEPRICES = 1.953 + 0.753InACCDT_{rate} - 0.813InPIRATE_{attacks} + 0.180InVANDALISM_{attacks} \quad (9)$$

This implies that a one percent annual increase in maritime accidents affecting tanker vessels in Nigerian leads to increasing trend in the crude oil prices in the international market by 0.753% while

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with a one percent increase in pirate attacks against oil tankers trading in Nigeria maritime domain, crude oil prices decreases by 0.813%. Similarly, a one percent increase in vandalism attacks against the overall offshore oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria leads to a 0.180% increase in the prices of crude oil in the international market.

The implication is that increasing oil tanker accident and increasing trend of vandalism attacks against oil and gas infrastructure in Nigeria maritime domain leads to increasing crude oil prices in the international market. The result also indicate that increasing rate of pirate attacks against oil tanker vessels trading in Nigeria, leads to decreasing trend crude oil prices in the market.

The coefficient of determination R^2 which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.663. This indicates that about 66% variation in the crude oil prices is explained by maritime safety and security incidents and challenges in the Nigerian maritime domain. The influence of maritime safety and security on trend of charter rate for offshore O&G service vessels over the years is presented in Table 8 below.

4.1 Test of Hypotheses

In this section, the various hypotheses proposed in the study were tested in order to draw inferences in line with the aim and objectives of the study.

Table 8: Test of hypothesis H_{01} : The extent of maritime safety and security incident rates of vessels involved in transportation of Nigerian seaborne oil trade is indeterminate

Variables/parameters	Incident Rate (IR)	Decision: <i>Accept H_{01} if $IR=0$</i>
Maritime safety (Tanker Accidents)	41.73	$41.73 > 0$; <i>Reject H_{01}</i>
Maritime security (Pirate attacks on oil tankers)	10.07	$10.07 > 0$; <i>Reject H_{01}</i>
Maritime Security (Vandalism attacks on O&G infrastructure)	2307.87	$2307.87 > 0$; <i>Reject H_{01}</i>

Source: Author's calculation. Decision: *Accept H_{01} if $IR=0$; Reject H_{01} if $IR > 0$.*

Table 8 shows that maritime safety with proxy as the frequency of oil tanker accident in Nigeria, maritime security with proxies as pirate attacks incident rate against oil tankers and vandalism attacks against the O&G infrastructure all have incident rates greater than zero. We therefore reject null hypothesis H_{01} and accept the alternate that the extent of maritime safety and security incidents rates of vessels involved in the transportation of Nigerian seaborne oil trade is determinate.

Table 9: Test of Hypothesis H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the extents of safety and security incidents affecting vessels involved in transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria

	Paired Differences		t	df	p-value = Sig. (2-tailed)
	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
	Upper				
Pair 2 Accidentrate - pirateattack	36.85175		13.099	14	.000
Pair 3 pirateattack - Vandalism	-1777.32442		-9.469	14	.000
Pair 4 Accidentrate - Vandalism	-1745.96307		-9.344	14	.000

Source: Author's calculation. Decision: *Accept null hypothesis H_{02} if p-value is greater than alpha (α) value of 0.05. (if p-value > 0.05 ; accept H_{02})*

The test of hypothesis H_{02} on Table 9 indicate that there is significant difference between oil tanker vessel accidents in Nigeria and pirate attacks against tanker vessels trading in Nigeria offshore O&G

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sector since p-value is less than the alpha value of 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$). This implies the frequency of tanker accidents is significantly higher than the frequency of pirate attacks against oil tanker vessels trading offshore Nigeria. It is significantly higher by 36.85 counts.

Similarly, there is a significant difference between pirate attacks against oil tankers in Nigeria waters and vandalism attacks against the O&G industry infrastructure in Nigeria. The vandalism attacks against the O&G infrastructure are significantly higher than pirate attacks against oil tankers by 1777.32 counts. This is confirmed by the p-value of 0.000 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$).

There is also a significant difference between vandalism attacks against offshore O&G infrastructure and oil tanker accidents in Nigeria with vandalism attacks being significantly higher by 1745.96 counts. The p-value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$) and this confirms the existence of significant difference.

We therefore reject null hypothesis H_{02} and accept the alternate that there is significant difference in the extents of safety and security incidents affecting vessels involved in transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria

Table10: Test of H_{03} : There is no significant influence of maritime safety and security incidents on the demand for oil tanker vessels in the Nigerian O&G industry

Hypotheses	F-cal.	F-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
H_{03}	4.306	3.68	0.033 ^b	Reject H_{03}
Variable	t-cal.	t-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
Accidentrate	-.032	1.75	.975	Not significant
pirateattack	.254	1.75	.804	Not significant
Vandalism	-2.410	1.75	.035	Significant

Source: Authors calculation. Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} > f\text{-critical}$; Accept null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} < F\text{-critical}$

The test of hypothesis H_{03} showed in table10 above shows F-score of 4.306, F-critical of 3.68, and p-value of 0.033. Since F-score is greater than F-critical, ($4.06 > 3.68$), we reject the null hypothesis H_{03} and accept the alternate. We conclude that there is significant influence of maritime safety and security incidents on the demand for oil tanker vessels in the Nigerian) O&G industry.

Similarly, t-test was conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of the tanker accidents, pirate attacks against oil tanker trading in Nigeria and vandalism attacks against the O&G industry infrastructure over the 15 years covered in the study. As shown in the table above, only vandalism attacks has t-cal score greater than t-critical ($2.410 > 1.75$). Thus only vandalism attacks against the O&G industry infrastructure have significant influence on the demand for oil tanker vessels in the offshore O&G sector in Nigeria. Oil tanker accidents and pirate attacks against oil tankers trading in Nigerian waters, all have t-cal. less than 1.75 ($-0.032 < 1.75$; and $-0.234 < 1$). As such, they have no significant influences on the demand for oil tanker vessels in the Nigerian O&G industry.

Table11: Test of H_{04a} : The relationship between Nigeria’s seaborne oil export trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents is not significant.

Hypotheses	F-cal.	F-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
H_{04}	3.796	3.68	0.042 ^b	Reject H_{04a}
Variable	t-cal.	t-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
Accidentrate	-1.134	1.75	.281	Not significant
pirateattack	-1.266	1.75	.232	Not significant
Vandalism	-.326	1.75	.750	Not significant

Source: Authors calculation. Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} > f\text{-critical}$; Accept null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} < F\text{-critical}$

The test of hypothesis H_{04a} shown in Table11 above shows F-score of 3.796, F-critical of 3.68, and p-value of 0.042. Since F-score is greater than F-critical, ($3.786 > 3.68$), we reject the null hypothesis H_{04a} and accept the alternate. We conclude that the relationship between Nigeria’s seaborne oil export trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents is significant.

Similarly, t-test was conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of the tanker accidents, pirate attacks against oil tanker trading in Nigeria and vandalism attacks against the O&G industry infrastructure over the 15 years covered in the study. As shown in the table above, none of the variables namely tanker accidents, pirate attacks against tankers and vandalism attacks have t-cal score greater than t-critical ($1.134 < 1.75$; $1.266 < 1.75$ and $0.326 < 1.75$). The variables individually have no significant effects on the seaborne oil export trade in Nigeria between 2006 and 2020.

Table12: Test of H_{04b} : The relationship between Nigeria’s seaborne oil import trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents is not significant.

Hypotheses	F-cal.	F-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
H_{04b}		4.905	0.040 ^b	Reject H_{04b}
Variable	t-cal.	t-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
Accidentrate	-1.135	1.75	.280	Not significant
pirateattack	-.401	1.75	.696	Not significant
Vandalism	-1.207	1.75	.253	Not significant

Source: Authors calculation. Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} > f\text{-critical}$; Accept null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} < F\text{-critical}$

The test of hypothesis H_{04b} showed in Table12 above shows F-score of 4.905, F-critical of 3.68, and p-value of 0.040. Since F-score is greater than F-critical, ($4.905 > 3.68$), we reject the null hypothesis H_{04b} and accept the alternate. We conclude that the relationship between Nigeria’s seaborne oil import trade and the trend of maritime safety cum security incidents is significant.

Similarly, t-test was conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of the tanker accidents, pirate attacks against oil tanker trading in Nigeria and vandalism attacks against the O&G industry infrastructure on seaborne oil import trade over the 15 years covered in the study. As shown in the table above, none of the variables namely tanker accidents, pirate attacks against tankers and vandalism attacks have t-cal score greater than t-critical ($1.135 < 1.75$; $0.401 < 1.75$ and $1.207 < 1.75$). The variables individually have no significant effects on the seaborne oil import trade in Nigeria between 2006 and 2020.

Table13: Test of H_{05} : The influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigeria on the trend of crude oil prices is not significant.

Hypotheses	F-cal.	F-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
H_{05}	7.216	3.68	0.006 ^b	Reject H_{05}
Variable	t-cal.	t-critical	p-value/sig.	Decision
Accidentrate	2.894	1.75	.015	Significant
pirateattack	-2.316	1.75	.041	Significant
Vandalism	1.409	1.75	.187	Not significant

Source: Authors calculation. Reject null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} > f\text{-critical}$; Accept null hypotheses if $F\text{-cal} < F\text{-critical}$

The test of hypothesis H_{05} showed in Table13 above shows F-score of 7.216, F-critical of 3.68, and p-value of 0.006. Since F-score is greater than F-critical, ($7.216 > 3.68$), we reject the null hypothesis H_{05} and accept the alternate. We conclude that the influence of maritime safety and security incidents in Nigeria on the trend of crude oil prices is significant.

Similarly, t-test was conducted to investigate the significance of the individual effects of the tanker accidents, pirate attacks against oil tanker trading in Nigeria and vandalism attacks against the O&G industry infrastructure over the 15 years covered in the study on crude oil prices. As shown in the table above, oil tanker accidents and pirate attacks against oil tankers trading Nigeria waters have significant influence on global crude oil prices over the period. Vandalism attacks with t-cal score that is less than t-critical ($1.09 < 1.75$) has no significant influence on crude oil prices in the market over the period.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The study establishes that maritime safety and security challenges significantly affect the transportation of seaborne oil trade in Nigeria. High rates of tanker accidents, piracy, and especially vandalism demonstrate systemic vulnerabilities in the maritime domain. While vandalism has the most pronounced negative impact on tanker demand and infrastructure, accidents and piracy also influence trade flows and crude oil price dynamics. Overall, maritime safety and security conditions are critical determinants of operational efficiency, investment stability, and economic performance in Nigeria's oil and gas sector.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the results and findings, the study recommended as follows:

- (i) Strengthen Maritime Security Architecture: Enhance naval patrols, surveillance technologies, and intelligence-sharing systems to combat piracy and vandalism in Nigerian waters.
- (ii) Improve Regulatory Enforcement: Ensure strict compliance with international maritime safety standards to reduce tanker accidents.
- (iii) Invest in Infrastructure Protection: Deploy advanced monitoring systems (e.g., drones, sensors) to safeguard offshore oil installations and pipelines.
- (iv) Capacity Building: Train maritime personnel and operators on safety procedures and emergency response systems.
- (v) Public-Private Collaboration: Encourage partnerships between government agencies and private stakeholders to fund and implement security initiatives.
- (vi) Policy Reforms: Develop integrated maritime security policies addressing root causes such as unemployment and militancy in coastal regions.

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